

HUMAN DEVELOPMENT SUMMARY CAPTURING ACHIEVEMENTS IN THE HDI AND COMPLEMENTARY METRICS THAT ESTIMATE GENDER GAPS, INEQUALITY, PLANETARY PRESSURES AND POVERTY. HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX

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The HDI is a summary measure for assessing long-term progress in three basic dimensions of human development: a long and healthy life, access to knowledge and a decent standard of living. Uzbekistan's HDI value for 2021 is 0,727— which put the country in the High human development category—positioning it at 101 out of 191 countries and territories.

Between 2000 and 2021, Uzbekistan's HDI value changed from 0,607 to 0,727, an change of 19.8 percent.

Between 2000 and 2021, Uzbekistan's life expectancy at birth changed by 5,1 years, mean years of schooling changed by 1,8 years and expected years of schooling changed by 1,7 years. Uzbekistan's GNI per capita changed by about 188.8 percent between 2000 and 2021.

Trends in Uzbekistan's HDI 1990-2021

HDI in comparison 1990-2021 Gender Development Index (GDI)

The GDI measures gender gaps in achievements in three basic dimensions of human development: health (measured by female and male life expectancy at birth), knowledge (measured by female and male expected years of schooling for children and mean years of schooling for adults aged 25 years and older) and living standards (measured by female and male estimated GNI per capita). It is a ratio of the female to the male HDI. The 2021 female HDI value for Uzbekistan is 0,703 in contrast with 0,744 for males, resulting in a GDI value of 0,944, placing it into Group 3.

Inequality-adjusted HDI (IHDI)

The IHDI considers inequalities in all three dimensions of the HDI by ‘discounting’ each dimension’s average value according to its level of inequality in the distribution. The ‘loss’ in human development due to inequality is given by the difference between the HDI and the IHDI. As the inequality in a country increases, the loss in human development also increases.

Gender Inequality index (GII)

The GII measures gender inequalities (the loss in human development due to inequality between female and male achievements) in three key dimensions – reproductive health, empowerment, and labour market. Reproductive health is measured by maternal mortality ratio and adolescent birth rates; empowerment is measured by the shares of parliamentary seats held and population with at least some secondary education by each gender; and labour market participation is measured by the labour force participation rates for women and men. Uzbekistan has a GII value of 0,227, ranking it 56 out of 170 countries in 2021.

Note: the lower GII values represent a better performance regarding gender inequality.

Gender Social Norms Index (GSNI)

Note: the lower GSNI values represent a better performance regarding GSNI.

The GSNI assesses the impact of social beliefs on gender equality across four dimensions, including political, educational, economic, and physical integrity. It draws upon data from 91 countries, encompassing the World Values Survey waves 5 (2005-2009), 6 (2010-2014), and 7 (2017-2022), with the latest update reflecting information as of 12 January 2023. The core GSNI measures the percentage of people with at least one bias. The GSNI ranges from 0 to 1. Higher GSNI values indicate higher biases against gender equality and women's empowerment.

Planetary pressures-adjusted HDI

The PHDI discounts the HDI for pressures on the planet to reflect a concern for intergenerational inequality. It is the level of human development adjusted by carbon dioxide emissions per person (production-based) and material footprint per capita to account for the excessive human pressure on the planet. In an ideal scenario where there are no pressures on the planet, the PHDI equals the HDI. However, as pressures increase, the PHDI falls below the HDI. In this sense, the PHDI measures the level of human development when planetary pressures are considered.

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